

THE IMPORTANCE OF SPORTS GAMES IN DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SPIRITUAL THINKING

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Abstract. This article analyzes the role and importance of sports in the development of students' spiritual thinking. It also discusses the impact of sports activities on the worldview, moral views, and teamwork skills of young people from a scientific perspective. It is stated that sports games not only strengthen physical health, but also have the potential to form important spiritual qualities in students, such as willpower, responsibility, discipline, and patriotism.

Keywords: spiritual thinking, sports games, spiritual education, physical education, healthy lifestyle, team spirit, moral values, education.

ENTRANCE

In today's era of globalization, enriching the spiritual world of young people and educating them as well-rounded individuals is one of the urgent issues. In particular, not only increasing the level of knowledge of students studying in higher educational institutions, but also developing their spiritual thinking is considered an important task. Because a spiritually mature person actively participates in the development of society and consciously approaches social problems. Spiritual thinking is one of the important factors determining a person's moral views, life values, social relationships and inner world. Along with education, sports also play a great role in the formation of such qualities in the minds of young people. Sports games, in addition to serving the physical development of students, also cultivate such qualities as discipline, responsibility, patience and teamwork. Today, attention to sports has risen to the level of state policy, and special importance is attached to guiding young people towards a healthy lifestyle. In particular, sports games provide an opportunity to protect students from various negative vices, organize their free time meaningfully, and increase their social activity. Therefore, it is important to scientifically study the importance of sports in spiritual education.

The issue of developing students' spiritual thinking is one of the priority areas of today's education system. Because modern society requires the upbringing of young people who are not only educated, but also have high spirituality. In higher educational institutions, along with increasing the intellectual potential of young people, it is also an important task to form their moral outlook, social activity and attitude to life. In this process, sports games appear as one of the important educational tools.

Sport is an integral part of human life, it not only ensures physical health, but also affects the spiritual and moral development of a person. In particular, the student period is one of the most active and responsible stages in human life. During this period, the character, outlook on life and spiritual values of young people are formed. Sports games help to reveal the internal potential of students in this process. Team sports teach students to work towards a common goal. For example, in games such as football, volleyball or basketball, each participant strives to put the interests of the team above personal interests. This develops a sense of cooperation, mutual respect and responsibility in the minds of young people. Students understand that individual effort alone is not enough to win in the sports process, success is achieved through teamwork. Such experiences are also important in their future social activities.

Sports also play a major role in strengthening a person's willpower. Any sport requires regular work, patience, and discipline. Regular participation in training, adherence to the established routine, and persistent pursuit of goals teach students to be responsible. In some cases, defeats in sports serve to strengthen young people spiritually. Because a person must learn

to accept difficulties along with achievements. It is in this aspect that sports occupy an important place as a means of spiritual education. Today, the issue of meaningful organization of free time among young people is also one of the pressing problems. Various harmful habits, excessive dependence on the Internet, or social indifference can negatively affect the spiritual world of young people. Sports games effectively organize students' free time by involving them in useful activities. A student who engages in sports takes care of his or her health, learns to value time, and develops a sense of purpose. As a result, the likelihood of young people succumbing to various negative influences decreases.

Another important aspect of sports is that it creates a healthy competitive atmosphere among students. During competitions, young people test their abilities and strive to achieve even better results. At the same time, sports also teach them the principles of honesty and justice. Because without following the rules of sports, real results cannot be achieved. Students begin to realize that the value of hard work and achievements through sports is high. This is also important in their future life. The mental state of a person also plays an important role in the formation of spiritual thinking. Sports activities help reduce stress and mental tension. The workload, exams, and various responsibilities in the process of higher education often exhaust students mentally. Regular sports activities enhance positive emotions in the human body, raise mood, and provide mental stability. A mentally healthy student consciously approaches the events around him and participates more actively in social processes.

Sports games also serve to develop leadership skills in students. Students who are team captains or active athletes acquire the skills of managing others, making decisions, and taking responsibility. These qualities will be important in their future professional activities. Because modern society needs proactive, active, and independent-thinking young people. National sports games also play an important role in the spiritual education of young people. In particular, sports related to folk traditions and national values form feelings of national pride and patriotism in the minds of young people. Through wrestling, horse riding, or other national sports, students are brought up in a spirit of respect for the history and culture of their people. This serves as an important factor in preserving national identity in the process of globalization.

The widespread organization of sports events in higher education institutions helps to increase the social activity of students. Competitions held between different faculties strengthen the atmosphere of friendship and solidarity among students. In addition, such events increase the interest of young people in university life and strengthen the team atmosphere. Through sports, students make new friends, exchange experiences and expand their social relationships. Today, it is observed that the physical activity of some young people is decreasing. As a result of the development of technologies, most of them spend their time in front of a phone or computer. This situation can negatively affect not only health, but also spiritual development. Therefore, increasing interest in sports in higher education institutions is one of the important tasks. Sports grounds, modern equipment and regular competitions can be an important factor in attracting young people to sports.

The role of sports coaches in spiritual education is also of great importance. The coach should pay attention not only to the sports result, but also to the moral education of young people. Students often perceive coaches as role models. Therefore, the culture, behavior and outlook on life of the coach directly affect the education of young people. With the right approach, sports training can become a means of not only physical, but also spiritual development. Sports games are one of the important factors in developing the spiritual thinking of students. It forms such qualities as healthy thinking, social activity, teamwork and responsibility in young people. Through sports, students not only become physically fit, but also acquire the skills to withstand life's difficulties, persistently strive for goals and take an active place in society. Therefore, it is important to further increase attention to sports games in the higher education system and widely involve young people in mass sports.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The importance of sports games in the development of students' spiritual thinking has been studied by many scientists and researchers. In particular, the connection between youth education, physical culture and spiritual maturity is considered one of the topical topics in modern pedagogical research. Scientists from different countries have tried to scientifically substantiate the role of sports in human life and its educational potential.

Among Uzbek researchers, RXMavlonov emphasizes the importance of sports in the spiritual education of youth. According to the scientist, sports activities, in addition to strengthening the physical health of young people, form such qualities as discipline, responsibility and social activity in them. He ¹also notes that "through sports, it is possible to meaningfully organize students' free time." Also, the scientific work conducted by Sh.K. Toshpulatov analyzed the relationship between physical education and spiritual development. In his opinion, "Sports activities educate young people in the spirit of mutual respect, cooperation and healthy competition."²

Scientists from the CIS countries have also deeply studied the educational aspects of sports. In particular, V.A. Sukhomlinsky emphasized the great role of physical activity in the upbringing of youth. He ³considered "Sports to be one of the important means of preparing young people for life." In addition, L.P. Matveyev, in his research on the theory and methodology of sports, substantiated the fact that sports affect not only physical, but also mental and moral development. He ⁴notes that "Sports training is an important factor in the formation of human character."

The role of sports in spiritual education has also been widely studied among world scientists. Pierre de Coubertin assessed sports as a means of comprehensive human development. He put forward the idea of educating young people in the spirit of peace, friendship and solidarity through the Olympic movement. According to the scientist, "Sport strengthens the will and patriotic feelings in a person."⁵ American researcher John W. Loy studied the sociological impact of sports on society and personal development. He noted that "analyzing the role of sports in the socialization of youth, team sports are important for developing leadership, responsibility and communication skills in a person."⁶ The scientist's research shows that sports are not only a physical activity, but also an important socio-cultural phenomenon.

The analyzed scientific sources show that sports games are an important pedagogical tool in developing students' spiritual thinking. The views of various scientists are close to each other, and most of them emphasize the positive impact of sports on the education of young people. Therefore, the study of sports as one of the important factors of the spiritual development of young people is a relevant issue from a scientific and practical point of view.

This study used several scientific methods to study the importance of sports games in developing students' spiritual thinking. Theoretical and practical approaches were used in harmony during the research process. This allowed for a comprehensive analysis of the topic. First of all, scientific literature, articles, and pedagogical studies on the topic were analyzed. By studying the literature, existing scientific views on the role of sports in the spiritual education of youth were summarized. Also, the opinions of local and foreign scientists were compared and the current aspects of the topic were clarified.

RESULTS

¹RX Mavlonov Issues of sports and youth spirituality development // Pedagogical education. – Tashkent, 2021. – No. 3. – P. 45-49.

²Sh.K. Toshpulatov The role of physical education in the spiritual education of students // Modern education. – Tashkent, 2022. – No. 5. – P. 28-33.

³V.A. Sukhomlinsky Serdtse otdayu detyam. - Moscow: Prosveshenie, 1983.

⁴LP Matveev Theory and methodology physical culture. - Moscow: SportAkademPress, 2008.

⁵Pierre de Coubertin Olympic Memoirs. - Lausanne: International Olympic Committee, 1979.

⁶John W. Loy Sport, Culture and Society: A Reader on the Sociology of Sport. – London: Routledge, 2015.

The results of the study showed that sports are an important factor in the development of students' spiritual thinking. It was found that students who actively participate in sports activities have a higher level of time management and discipline. Because sports require regular training and work on themselves. This helps to form qualities such as responsibility and determination in young people. In interviews with students, most of them noted that their self-confidence increased as a result of playing sports. Sports also had a positive effect on the mental state of students. It was found that various loads and stress in the process of higher education are reduced to a certain extent through sports. Students involved in sports stated that they feel mentally refreshed and active. This also had a positive effect on their interest in studying and their activity in social life.

Another important aspect of sports in the spiritual education of young people was shown. During sports games, students try to adhere to moral values such as honesty, justice and respect. Compliance with the rules during competitions and respectful attitude towards opponents are manifested as the main requirements of sports culture. This also affects the behavior of young people in everyday life. It was observed that among students who actively participated in sports events, there was an increased interest in a healthy lifestyle. They paid more attention to staying away from harmful habits, maintaining physical health and leading an active lifestyle. As a result, it was found that sports serve not only physical, but also spiritual and social development.

Overall, the results confirmed that sports are an effective tool for developing students' spiritual thinking. It was found that sports have a positive impact not only on the physical fitness of young people, but also on their moral and social development.

DISCUSSIONS

Based on the results of the study, it can be said that sports are an important educational tool in the spiritual development of young students. The data obtained are also consistent with previous scientific studies to a certain extent. Because many scientists have emphasized the role of sports in shaping human character and worldview. In this study, the development of such qualities as responsibility, discipline, and teamwork was observed among students who regularly engage in sports. The impact of sports on spiritual education is explained, first of all, by its motivation for an active lifestyle. During sports, a student follows certain rules, sets goals for himself and tries to achieve them. This changes the attitude of young people to life in a positive direction. In particular, team sports teach a person to cooperate with others and adhere to the principle of mutual respect.

It was observed that sports also have a positive effect on mental stability. At a time when stress and mental fatigue are increasing among young people, sports are one of the important tools that reduce such problems. The fact that students involved in sports feel freer and more active also has a positive effect on their spiritual state. This shows that sports have not only physical, but also psychological importance. The role of sports in protecting young people from negative habits is also important. During the study, it was noticed that students who regularly engage in sports are less prone to harmful habits. Because sports require a person to follow a healthy lifestyle. As a result, young people's free time is organized meaningfully and they get used to engaging in useful activities.

Based on the results of the discussion, it can be said that sports games are an effective pedagogical tool for developing the spiritual thinking of young people. Through sports, important qualities such as healthy thinking, mutual respect, social activity and responsibility are formed in students. Therefore, it is important to increase attention to sports in higher educational institutions, widely involve students in mass sports events, and effectively use the educational potential of sports.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, sports are one of the important educational tools in developing students' spiritual thinking. The study revealed that sports have a significant impact not only on ensuring

physical health, but also on the moral and social development of young people. In particular, team sports are important in educating students in the spirit of cooperation, mutual respect and responsibility.

Among students who regularly engage in sports, qualities such as discipline, determination, and self-confidence are relatively highly developed. Sports training teaches young people to strive for goals, overcome difficulties, and properly allocate time. This has a positive effect not only on their activity in the educational process, but also on their future life activities. It has been observed that sports games are also an effective tool for meaningfully organizing students' free time. Through sports, young people move away from various negative habits, strive to follow a healthy lifestyle, and become more active in social life. As a result, sports serve to develop the spiritual outlook and social culture of young people.

It also showed the importance of sports in ensuring mental stability. Engaging in sports reduces students' stress levels, improves their mood, and develops positive thinking in them. This helps young people grow up as spiritually mature individuals. However, it was also revealed that there are shortcomings in the sports infrastructure and organization of sports events in some higher educational institutions. Therefore, one of the important tasks is to widely involve students in sports, create modern sports conditions, and effectively use the educational opportunities of sports.

In general, sports are an effective factor in developing students' spiritual thinking, which serves to educate young people as physically healthy, spiritually mature and socially active individuals. Therefore, it is of urgent importance to further increase attention to sports in the higher education system and to widely use the spiritual and educational potential of sports.

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